

**Prosecutor's supervision over the implementation of legislation on
industrial waste**

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It is worth mentioning that it is not among the regulatory legal acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which is why it is worth resorting to the study of scientific works written by both domestic and foreign authors. Next, in the opinion of the author, more understandable and specific definitions of this term will be listed. According to Nikolai Pavlovich Dudin, the author of the scientific article “Prosecutorial supervision as a special type of state activity,” it is an independent type of state activity, which is aimed at ensuring the rule of law, ensuring unity and strengthening the rule of law, ensuring the protection of human and civil rights and freedoms, as well as ensuring protection of legally protected interests of society and the state. It is worth noting that in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the Prosecutor’s Office”, namely in Article 2, where the main tasks of this body are mentioned, almost everything that was previously mentioned is listed, from which we can conclude that all the tasks of such a body as the prosecutor’s office, and are carried out through prosecutorial supervision.

According to Yakubina Yu.P., the author of the scientific work “Prosecutorial supervision as a type of state activity,” this term represents an independent and main direction of activity of the prosecutor’s office, implemented by a special entity, that is, a centralized unified system of prosecutor’s offices, aimed at ensuring the rule of law and promoting formation and development of a democratic rule of law state.

I would like to add that prosecutorial supervision, according to the previously mentioned Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the Prosecutor’s Office,” has several areas, for example, supervision over the observance of the rights and freedoms of citizens and supervision over the implementation of laws, which is subject to discussion during the writing of this work. Article 20 of this law describes the subject of this type of supervision, which, according to this article, is control over compliance with legislation by various bodies and enterprises, as well as verification of compliance of their actions with the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, namely in Article 143, states that supervision over the accurate and uniform implementation of laws on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan is carried out by the Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the prosecutors subordinate to him, which is additional evidence of the exclusivity of the right of the prosecutor's office to supervise the activities other government bodies and enterprises.

Having studied the regulatory legal acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as scientific articles by theorists and practitioners, the author of this work can come to the conclusion that the term “prosecutorial supervision” is a systematic control carried out by the prosecutor’s office, aimed at ensuring compliance with the

rule of law in the activities of authorities and enterprises, institutions and citizens, which covers verification of the implementation of laws, government acts, as well as the compliance of their actions with the Constitution and laws of the country. Prosecutorial supervision is aimed at preventing and identifying offenses, protecting the rights and legitimate interests of citizens, as well as maintaining the proper functioning of the legal order in society, and is also an important element of public administration and guarantees the execution of laws, maintaining legal stability and public order. In addition, I would like to add that prosecutorial supervision contributes to the development of the rule of law, strengthening the legal culture and respect for the rights and freedoms of citizens.

The next thing to be studied, due to the importance of its full understanding in writing this work, is the definition of the term “industrial waste”. According to the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On approval of the regulations on the procedure for state accounting and control in the field of waste management”, waste is the remains of various materials, raw materials, semi-finished products or products that arise as a result of production or consumer processes, which also includes goods that have lost their original consumer value. From the text of this paragraph it can be understood that waste can be either consumer waste, which, according to Viktor Ivanovich Skantsev, author of the scientific article “Problems of recycling production and consumption waste,” represents material residues arising in the process of using goods and services by end consumers that require disposal or processing, and production, which, according to Boboaiçh B.B., author of the book “Processing of Industrial Waste,” are remnants of raw materials, materials and semi-finished products that arise during the manufacturing process and have lost their original value or do not meet

standards. These residues, after the necessary processing, can be used as part of the production or consumer process, including the possibility of their use in the production of by-products.

Due to the specifics of the topic of the dissertation work, the author will consider only industrial wastes, most of which, it is worth mentioning, according to Appendix No. 1 of the Basel Convention “On the Control of Transboundary Movements of Hazardous Wastes and Their Disposal”, are included in the category of substances “subject to regulation”, then there are dangers.

The last thing that needs to be mentioned is the repeated listing and establishment of requirements for waste management, that is, for their storage, disposal, collection, sale and processing, both in the previous Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Waste” and in the Resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers “On approval of regulations in the field of waste management” and “On approval of the regulations on the procedure for state accounting and control in the field of waste management.” It follows from this that all actions to be performed with waste are specifically and clearly described in regulatory legal acts, over which the prosecutor’s supervision studied by the author is carried out.

Next, I would like to resort to a retrospective analysis of prosecutorial supervision. If we talk about what this type of analysis is and why it was chosen for use by the author of this work, then it is worth mentioning the definition of it from A.V. Machnev, the author of the scientific work “Methodology of retrospective analysis - an elementary tool for preliminary justification of complex systems” , which noted that retrospective analysis is a study of data covering changes over time, ranging from past periods to the present, which distinguishes this type of analysis

from other forms in that it compares current indicators with historical data, which helps optimize parameters and manage risks in the future. That is, to simplify this definition, this type of analysis is a research methodology aimed at analyzing the historical process of formation and development of a subject, be it an organization, an individual or a phenomenon, namely the analysis of previous events, actions and decisions made in the past in order to identify and understanding their influence on the current state and characteristics of the subject, thereby making it possible to trace the dynamics of changes, highlight key stages of development and identify the factors that determine its current position.

This type of analysis was chosen by the author of this work for the reason that it is with the help of it that it will be possible to comprehensively and completely study not only the concept and role of prosecutorial supervision, but also the causes and circumstances that contributed to its emergence and development.

If we move on to the most retrospective analysis of prosecutorial supervision, then it is worth starting with the history of the USSR as the predecessor of both the legislative framework of our country and the Republic of Uzbekistan as a state as a whole. Having studied the scientific article “The history of the formation of prosecutorial supervision over the implementation of federal legislation as a separate area of activity of the prosecutor’s office,” the authors of which are S.A. Goncharov. and Abramov E.A., the following stages of the emergence and development of prosecutorial supervision can be distinguished:

1. For the first time this concept was introduced in legal practice in the directive order of the Assistant Prosecutor of the Republic Radus-Zenkovich No. 105 “On issues of the immediate activities of local prosecutors for general

supervision,” published in the Weekly of Soviet Justice of 1922 No. 37/38. It is worth noting that, according to the previously mentioned authors, initially prosecutors focused on regulations relating exclusively to the financial sector of society, that is, they checked the legality and validity of decisions made by local authorities in the field of taxes and the activities of enterprises.

2. Later, in the Regulations “On the Supreme Court of the RSFSR” of 1923, the concept of prosecutorial supervision was introduced, which covered the activities of prosecutors to ensure compliance with the law by central and local authorities. These authors also note that prosecutors did not always correctly interpret the functions assigned to them, focusing on checking maternity hospitals, theaters and similar places, while the activities of leading ministries and institutions, as well as the decisions they made, were left without due attention.

3. Years later, the Decrees of the Central Executive Committee and the Council of People's Commissars of the USSR "On the Prosecutor's Office of the USSR" dated December 17, 1933 were adopted, which amended the Regulations "On the Prosecutor's Office of the USSR", thereby limiting their functions in the field of general supervision, as well as establishing control over the decisions of individual departments of the country, as well as decrees and orders of the USSR Government.

4. In 1944, the order of the Prosecutor General of the USSR “On strengthening general supervision over the precise implementation of laws” No. 128 was issued, which defined the tasks and functions of the prosecutor’s office in this area, including assigning them the responsibility of receiving applications and reports from citizens about illegal actions of state and local authorities.

5. In 1995, a draft of a new Federal Law “On the Prosecutor's Office of the Russian Federation” No. 168 was developed, which provided for the division of tasks and functions of supervision into new areas of activity, namely supervision of the implementation of laws, as well as the observance of human and civil rights and freedoms.

The listed events formed the basis of the prosecutorial supervision that functions today, which, according to Article 4 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the Prosecutor’s Office,” covers all spheres of life and activity of society, namely, it is divided into supervision, for example, over compliance with laws in places of detention; for the implementation of laws aimed at combating tax and currency crimes; for compliance with laws in the Armed Forces and so on, that is, for greater efficiency and scope, it is already divided into many areas.

Having dealt with the reasons and circumstances that contributed to the emergence of the concept of prosecutorial supervision, it is worth moving on to the reasons that cemented the importance of prosecutorial supervision over the implementation of legislation on industrial waste. As previously mentioned, the ecological state in the country began, due to its visibility, to worry the population of our country, as it contributed to the emergence of both air and natural pollution, noticeable even to the naked eye, and some diseases associated with it. From everything that has been said previously, we can come to the conclusion that the catalyst for prosecutorial supervision over the implementation of legislation on industrial waste was the following:

1. As stated, industrial development and an increase in production volumes are accompanied by improper management of industrial waste, which leads to soil,

water and air pollution, deterioration of public health and destruction of ecosystems. Prosecutor's supervision is necessary to monitor compliance with the law and prevent negative environmental consequences.

2. Uncontrolled accumulation and disposal of industrial waste can pose a threat to public health, causing various diseases and poisoning. Prosecutor's supervision promotes compliance with safety and health standards, ensuring the protection of citizens' rights to a favorable environment.

3. Awareness of the need to preserve natural resources for future generations and ensure sustainable development has become a key trend in world politics and economics. Prosecutor's supervision helps reduce the negative impact of production processes on the environment, contributing to the implementation of the principles of sustainable development.

Further, if we talk about a retrospective analysis of industrial waste, then it is worth turning to the authors of such scientific articles as “On the issue of inventory, classification and neutralization of industrial waste from territorial-industrial complexes in the conditions of Uzbekistan”, Usmanov I.A. and Khasanova M.I., “On the issue of the formation of the industry for processing and disposal of waste (production and consumption waste)”, Belkharoev H.U., as well as “Changes in the sectoral structure and spatial organization of industry in the world”, Rodionova I.A. ., the study of whose works made it possible to draw the following conclusions:

- Between the early 2000s and the mid-2010s, there was a significant increase in the total volume of industrial waste in the country. This was due to the expansion of industrial production, especially in the petrochemical, textile and food processing sectors. The increase in waste volumes created problems both with disposal and with pollution of water and air resources.

- Since the mid-2010s, the government of Uzbekistan began to actively implement programs to reduce the volume of industrial waste and increase their effective disposal. This included the introduction of modern production technologies with minimal waste generation, the creation of a waste collection and

recycling system, the classification and separation of waste into types, the establishment of rules for their collection, transportation and disposal, as provided for in the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On approval of regulatory acts in the field of waste management.”

- В результате этих усилий, с 2020 года отмечается стабилизация и даже некоторое снижение общего объема производственных отходов в стране. Это достигается за счет внедрения более эффективных производственных процессов, а также развития отрасли переработки отходов. Примером может служить Приказ Президента Республики Узбекистан «О мерах по трансформации сферы экологии и охраны окружающей среды и организации деятельности уполномоченного государственного органа» от 31.05.2023 года, который предусматривает внедрение принципа «ноль отходов», который направлен на максимальное уменьшение возникновения отходов в Республике Узбекистан.